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**E5.1 Intermediate prototype for high
precision smart telemetry: A
Comprehensive Guide to Enhanced
System Insight
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List of Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
OTLP	OpenTelemetry Protocol
UI	User Interface
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
QoE	Quality of Experience
SLO	Service Level Objective
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

Table 1 Acronyms

System Architecture and Data Flow

Overview

This documents the architecture and data flow of an integrated telemetry, monitoring, and tracing system. The system is designed to collect, process, and analyze telemetry data, providing insights into system performance and enabling proactive monitoring and alerting.

Architecture Components

Edge Cluster Simulation

- **Metrics Mock Project:** Simulates raw telemetry data, acting as a source of telemetry metrics for testing and development.
 - **Endpoint:** `http://localhost:8000`

Cloud Cluster Simulation

- **Synchronization Collector:** Processes data from the Metrics Mock Project for synchronization.
- **Synchronization Integration:** Integrates processed data across the system, facilitating data flow and analysis.
 - **Endpoint:** `http://localhost:8002/synchronization`
- **Observability APIs:** Processes and makes data available for monitoring, analysis, and alerting.
 - **Endpoint:** `http://localhost:8003/process_metrics`
- **Alarm Integration:** Generates alarms based on processed data, integrating with external alarm management APIs.
 - **Endpoint:** `http://localhost:8004/create_alarm`
- **InfluxDB Integration:** Manages the storage of time-series data in InfluxDB.

External Components

- **InfluxDB:** Stores and provides access to time-series data.
 - **Endpoint:** <http://localhost:8086>
- **Prometheus:** Monitors the system, scraping metrics for operational insights.
 - **Endpoint:** <http://localhost:9090>
- **Jaeger:** Offers distributed tracing to monitor and troubleshoot transactions across the system.
 - **UI Endpoint:** <http://localhost:16686>
 - **OTLP Collector Endpoint:** Collects traces on port **4317**
- **TM Forum API:** An external API for alarm management, integrated with Alarm Integration for creating and managing alarms.
 - **Endpoint:** <http://localhost:8642/tmf-api/alarmManagement/v5>

Data Flow Diagram

Figure 1. Project Data Flow

Component Descriptions and Integrations

- **Metrics Mock Project:** Initiates the data flow by generating telemetry data to simulate an edge computing environment.

- **Synchronization Collector & Integration:** These components work together to collect, process, and integrate telemetry data across the system.
- **Observability APIs:** Acts as the central hub for processed data, facilitating observability, monitoring, and alerting.
- **Alarm Integration & TM Forum API:** Manages the generation and handling of alarms based on processed telemetry data.
- **InfluxDB Integration & InfluxDB:** Stores processed telemetry data for long-term analysis and querying.
- **Prometheus & Jaeger:** Provide monitoring and tracing capabilities, respectively, enhancing the system's observability.

Usage

This system architecture is designed for comprehensive observability of telemetry data, supporting a wide range of use cases from performance monitoring to troubleshooting and alerting. Each component plays a critical role in ensuring data is collected, processed, and analyzed effectively.

Mock Metrics Project

Overview

The Mock Metrics Project is a FastAPI application designed to simulate telemetry data for various metrics, such as latency, bandwidth utilization, and quality of experience (QoE). This service is particularly useful for testing data collection, monitoring systems, and integration with telemetry platforms without the need for real, hardware-generated data.

Setup and Installation

Requirements

- Python 3.7+ installed.
- FastAPI and Uvicorn installed. Install these packages using pip:

```
pip install fastapi uvicorn
```

Running the Service

To run the mock metrics service, use the following command:

```
uvicorn main:app --host 0.0.0.0 --port 8000
```

This command starts the FastAPI application on port 8000, making the mock telemetry data endpoints available.

Available Endpoints

The service provides several endpoints, each simulating different types of telemetry data:

- **/metrics/data_sync**: Returns a list of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to data synchronization metrics.
- **/metrics/latency**: Simulates latency measurements.
- **/metrics/bandwidth**: Generates bandwidth utilization data.
- **/metrics/qoe**: Provides Quality of Experience (QoE) ratings.
- **/metrics/3d_model_accuracy**: Simulates accuracy metrics for 3D models.
- **/metrics/volumetric_video**: Generates data on volumetric video encoding efficiency.
- **/metrics/resource_allocation**: Simulates resource allocation efficiency metrics.
- **/metrics/ai_model_update**: Generates metrics on AI model update and deployment times.
- **/metrics/network_load**: Simulates network load and scalability metrics.

Each endpoint returns data in a structured format, including a timestamp, server identifier, a list of metrics (with name, value, unit, and type), temperature in Celsius, and custom tags for additional context. **It should be in a different project, but for this case, like a simple mock, is added into `mocks/metric_exporter.py`.**

Data Model

Metric

Defines a single telemetry metric, including its name, value, unit, and type.

KPI

Represents a set of metrics collected at a particular time, including additional details like server identification, temperature, and tags for contextual information.

Synchronization Collector

Overview

The **synchronization_collector.py** script is part of the telemetry system designed to collect and forward synchronization metrics asynchronously. This script is built on Python's **asyncio** and **aiohttp** libraries to perform non-blocking network operations efficiently. It also integrates OpenTelemetry for tracing, allowing for detailed observation and monitoring of its operations.

Configuration

The script operates based on several environment variables:

- **BASE_URL**: The base URL of the service from which synchronization metrics are collected.
- **INTEGRATION_URL**: The endpoint to which the collected data is forwarded for integration.
- **OTLP_ENDPOINT**: The endpoint for the OpenTelemetry Protocol (OTLP) exporter, used for tracing data export.

Components

OpenTelemetry Tracing Initialization

Tracing is configured using OpenTelemetry to monitor the script's behavior, with spans exported to an OTLP endpoint. The tracing setup includes a **TracerProvider** and a **BatchSpanProcessor**, facilitating the collection and export of trace data.

Data Collector Classes

DataCollector

A base class providing a structure for data collection tasks. It includes an asynchronous method **collect_data_async** intended for implementation by subclasses.

SynchronizationCollector

This subclass implements asynchronous data collection and forwarding. It fetches synchronization metrics from a specified URL and sends this data to an integration service.

Main Asynchronous Routine

The script's entry point is the **main** function, which runs asynchronously. It creates an **aiohttp.ClientSession**, instantiates a **SynchronizationCollector**, and executes the data collection and forwarding process.

Key Functions

`collect_and_forward_metrics_async`

Collects synchronization metrics and forwards them to an integration service. It uses **asyncio** for asynchronous HTTP requests and handles both successful and unsuccessful responses, logging the outcomes accordingly.

`send_data_to_integration`

Sends collected data to the integration service. It creates a new span for tracing this operation, providing visibility into the success or failure of data forwarding.

Usage

To run the script, ensure that Python 3.7 or newer is installed along with the required packages (**asyncio**, **aiohttp**, **opentelemetry**). Set the necessary environment variables for configuration, then execute the script:

```
python synchronization_collector.py
```

Synchronization Integration Service

Overview

The **synchronization_integration.py** script is a core component of the telemetry system designed to receive, process, and forward synchronization metrics to observability tools and services. It is built using FastAPI for handling HTTP requests and integrates with OpenTelemetry and Prometheus for metrics collection and monitoring.

Features

- **Metrics Collection:** Receives synchronization metrics from various sources.
- **Metrics Processing:** Processes and transforms metrics into a suitable format for observability tools.
- **Prometheus Integration:** Exports metrics to Prometheus for monitoring and alerting.
- **Alarm Triggering:** Triggers alarms based on predefined conditions in the metrics.

Configuration

Before running the script, ensure the following prerequisites are met:

- Python 3.7+ is installed.
- Required Python packages (**fastapi**, **uvicorn**, **httpx**, **prometheus_client**, **opentelemetry**) are installed.

Set up necessary environment variables if needed, and configure the Prometheus metric reader to listen on the appropriate port (default: 9464).

Running the Service

To start the service, use the following command:

```
uvicorn synchronization_integration:app --host 0.0.0.0 --port 8002
```

This command starts the FastAPI application on port 8002.

API Endpoints

POST /synchronization

Receives a list of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) containing various metrics. Each KPI includes:

- Timestamp
- Server identification
- A list of metrics (name, value, unit, type)
- Temperature in Celsius
- Additional tags for context

The endpoint processes these metrics, updating Prometheus instruments accordingly, and may trigger alarms based on specific conditions.

Models

Metric

Defines a single metric's structure, including its name, value, unit, and type. The type can be one of the following: "gauge", "counter", "histogram", "upDownCounter".

KPI

Represents a set of metrics collected at a particular time, including server identification, temperature, and tags for additional context.

Metrics Processing

Upon receiving data, the service processes each metric according to its type, updating Prometheus metrics and potentially triggering alarms for anomalous values.

Prometheus Integration

Metrics are exposed to Prometheus using a **PrometheusMetricReader**, allowing for monitoring and alerting based on the collected data.

Alarm Triggering

The service can trigger alarms for specific metric conditions, integrating with observability APIs to notify of potential issues.

Observability APIs Service

Overview

The **observability_apis.py** script serves as a cornerstone within our observability framework, facilitating real-time metrics processing and alerting based on specific criteria. It is built on FastAPI for efficient HTTP API handling, integrates seamlessly with InfluxDB for robust time-series data management, and incorporates TM Forum's QoS for nuanced service level objective (SLO) monitoring and management.

Features

- **Metrics Processing:** Accepts and processes a list of metrics sent through HTTP POST requests.
- **InfluxDB Integration:** Stores processed metrics in InfluxDB for time-series analysis.
- **Alert Triggering:** Evaluates metrics against thresholds to trigger alerts.

Configuration

Ensure the following prerequisites are met before running the script:

- Python 3.7+ installed.
- Required Python packages (**fastapi**, **uvicorn**, **httpx**, **requests**, **pydantic**, **influxdb_client**) installed.
- InfluxDB and any other dependent services are running and accessible.

Running the Service

To start the service, run the following command:

```
uvicorn observability_apis:app --host 0.0.0.0 --port 8003
```

This command starts the FastAPI application on port 8003, making the observability APIs available for receiving metrics.

API Endpoints

POST /process_metrics

Accepts a JSON payload of metrics, each comprising:

- **Name:** Unique identifier of the metric.
- **Value:** Quantitative measure or value of the metric.
- **Type:** Category of the metric (e.g., "histogram", "counter", "gauge", "upDownCounter").
- **Tags:** A key-value pair dictionary providing additional context.
- **Timestamp:** Time at which the metric was recorded.

Metrics are then processed for storage in InfluxDB and evaluated for any alert-triggering conditions.

Models

MetricData

Defines the structure for incoming metrics, including their name, value, type, tags, and timestamp.

Metric

Simplifies the structure for metric processing within the service, aligning closely with **MetricData** for operational consistency.

InfluxDB Integration

Metrics are written to InfluxDB using the **InfluxDBIntegration** class. This includes transforming the metric data into the appropriate format for InfluxDB and handling any errors that occur during the write operation.

Alert Triggering

The script includes logic to evaluate each metric against predefined thresholds. If a metric exceeds these thresholds, an alert is triggered using the **trigger_alarm** function, which sends an alarm creation request to a configured endpoint.

InfluxDB Integration Module

Overview

The `influxdb_integration.py` script is designed to facilitate the integration of Python applications with InfluxDB, a time-series database. It provides a straightforward interface for connecting to an InfluxDB instance, writing data points, and executing queries. This module abstracts the complexities of dealing with the InfluxDB Client Library and offers a simplified approach for handling time-series data.

Configuration

Requirements

- InfluxDB server (local or remote) setup and accessible
- Python 3.7+ installed
- InfluxDB Python client library installed (`influxdb-client` package)
- An `influxdb.properties` file containing necessary configuration details

Configuration File

The module reads database connection settings from an `influxdb.properties` file, which should include the following sections and keys:

```
[influxdb]
token = YourInfluxDBAuthToken
org = YourOrganizationName
url = http://localhost:8086
bucket = YourBucketName
```

Ensure this file is placed in a suitable location, and its path is correctly referenced in the `InfluxDBIntegration` class constructor.

Class InfluxDBIntegration

Initialization

The `InfluxDBIntegration` class is initialized with the path to the configuration file. It establishes a connection to the InfluxDB instance using the specified settings.

Writing Data

- **Method:** `async write_data(self, measurement, tags, fields, timestamp=None)`
- **Description:** Asynchronously writes data to the specified InfluxDB bucket. Data points are defined by measurements, tags, fields, and optionally, a timestamp.
- **Parameters:**
 - **measurement:** The name of the measurement (string).
 - **tags:** A dictionary of tag names and values.
 - **fields:** A dictionary of field names and values.
 - **timestamp:** Optional. The timestamp for the data point (in nanoseconds).

Querying Data

- **Method:** `query_data(self, flux_query)`
- **Description:** Executes a Flux query against the connected InfluxDB instance and returns the results.
- **Parameters:**
 - **flux_query:** The Flux query string to be executed.

TM Forum Alarm Integration Module

Overview

The `alarm_integration.py` script facilitates the integration with TM Forum's alarm management API. It is designed to interact with an alarm management system by creating, acknowledging, and clearing alarms via HTTP requests. This module is built using FastAPI and httpx for asynchronous HTTP operations, making it suitable for high-performance web applications.

Configuration

Requirements

- A running instance of a TM Forum-compatible alarm management system.
- Python 3.7+ installed.
- FastAPI and httpx libraries installed.

Environment Setup

Ensure the alarm management system's API endpoint is accessible and the required environment for running an Async FastAPI application is set up, including:

- Installation of FastAPI: **pip install fastapi**
- Installation of httpx: **pip install httpx**
- Installation of Uvicorn for serving the application: **pip install uvicorn**

Alarm Management Operations

The module provides three primary operations related to alarm management:

1. **Create Alarm:** Submits a new alarm to the alarm management system.
2. **Acknowledge Alarm:** Marks an alarm as acknowledged within the alarm management system.
3. **Clear Alarm:** Clears an alarm from the alarm management system.

Usage

Instantiation

Create an instance of the **TMForumAlarmIntegration** class, optionally specifying the alarm API URL:

```
tm_forum_alarm = TMForumAlarmIntegration(alarm_api_url='http://your-alarm-api-endpoint/tmf-api/alarmManagement/v5')
```

Creating an Alarm

To create an alarm, prepare a dictionary containing the alarm data according to the TM Forum's alarm management API specification and call the **create_alarm** method. There is an example in **mocks/alarm.py**.

Acknowledging an Alarm

To acknowledge an alarm, prepare the acknowledgment data and call the **ack_alarm** method. There is an example in **mocks/alarm.py**.

Clearing an Alarm

To clear an alarm, prepare the clearing data and call the **clear_alarm** method. There is an example in **mocks/alarm.py**.

FastAPI Endpoints

The script also defines FastAPI endpoints for creating, acknowledging, and clearing alarms through HTTP POST requests, making it easy to integrate these operations into web applications or external systems.

Integrated Telemetry, Monitoring, and Tracing System Setup

This guide details the steps to deploy InfluxDB, Prometheus, and Jaeger, offering a robust platform for handling metrics, logs, and traces for observability into applications.

System Components

- **InfluxDB:** A time-series database designed to handle high write and query loads, ideal for storing telemetry data.
- **Prometheus:** An open-source monitoring system with a dimensional data model, flexible query language, and alerting functionality.
- **Jaeger:** A distributed tracing system that provides transaction monitoring and root cause analysis, as well as service dependency analysis.

Prerequisites

- Docker or Podman installed on your system.
- Basic understanding of containerization and networking.
- Configuration files prepared for Prometheus.

Installation and Configuration Steps

Running InfluxDB

Start an InfluxDB container to store and manage time-series data:

```
podman run -p 8086:8086 -v myInfluxVolume:/var/lib/influxdb2 influxdb:latest
```

This command mounts **myInfluxVolume** for data persistence and exposes the InfluxDB UI and API on port 8086.

Preparing Prometheus Configuration

Create a **prometheus.yml** file with the following content to configure Prometheus to scrape metrics:

```
global:
  scrape_interval: 15s
  evaluation_interval: 15s

scrape_configs:
  - job_name: 'fastapi'
    static_configs:
      - targets: ['host.docker.internal:9464']
```

This configuration sets Prometheus to scrape metrics every 15 seconds from a FastAPI application.

Running Prometheus

Deploy Prometheus using the prepared configuration:

```
podman run -d --name prometheus -p 9090:9090 -v  
"/path/to/prometheus.yml:/etc/prometheus/prometheus.yml" prom/prometheus
```

Ensure to replace **"/path/to/prometheus.yml"** with the actual path to your configuration file.

Running Jaeger

Deploy Jaeger for collecting and viewing traces:

```
podman run --name jaeger -e COLLECTOR_OTLP_ENABLED=true -p 16686:16686 -p 4317:4317  
-p 4318:4318 jaegertracing/all-in-one:1.35
```

This setup enables Jaeger's UI on port 16686 and configures it to receive traces via OTLP.

Accessing UIs

- **InfluxDB UI:** Accessible at **http://localhost:8086**.
- **Prometheus UI:** Accessible at **http://localhost:9090**.
- **Jaeger UI:** Accessible at **http://localhost:16686**.